

Carrier-Phase Recovery for Coherent Optical Systems: Algorithms, Challenges and Solutions

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Abstract—Carrier phase recovery (CPR) is a key digital signal processing (DSP) subsystem in optical fiber communications. In this paper, we review recent advances in CPR algorithms and analyze their performance under the impact of different system impairments in a long-haul 256 GBaud setting. We study both single- and dual-stage CPR configurations, in the linear and nonlinear regimes, and at different system baud rates. By exploiting CPR algorithms tailored for digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) systems, we are able to reap the benefits of their intrinsic resilience to the two main performance-limiting effects of optical fiber systems: equalization enhanced phase noise (EEPN) and nonlinear interference (NLI). Overall, the paper sheds light on the potential benefits of DSCM and highlights the need for further research into CPR algorithms that specifically target the effect of nonlinear phase noise (NLPN).

Index Terms—Coherent optical communications, digital signal processing, carrier-phase recovery, digital subcarrier multiplexing, nonlinear phase noise.

I. INTRODUCTION

CARRIER-phase recovery (CPR) was arguably a key enabler of digital coherent systems as we know them today [1]. Throughout the years, CPR has been a subject of extensive research, demanding inventive and low-complexity solutions to track and compensate phase noise (PN) in coherent transmission.

As the name implies, PN is considered any noise in the system that manifests as an unintended phase rotation in the received signal. Since in coherent systems, the information is carried not only in amplitude but also in phase; this noise must be compensated for, in order to retrieve the sent information. Phase noise was historically mainly attributed to the frequency jitter of the transmitter and local oscillator (LO) lasers, resulting in their non-null spectral line width. Since PN was thus mostly caused by the carrier lightwave, that is why the digital signal processing (DSP) subsystem aiming to compensate for PN is still to this day called *carrier-phase recovery*. However, with the improvement of commercially

available lasers, a new type of PN impairment is becoming dominant and considered when designing CPR algorithms: nonlinear phase noise (NLPN) [2]. The problem with NLPN is that it is usually harder to compensate for, given its short-time correlation and frequency dependence [3]. For that reason, the mitigation of NLPN is currently one of the main drivers for research in CPR algorithms [4]–[8].

Also playing an unexpectedly relevant role in the performance of CPR algorithms is chromatic dispersion (CD). While chromatic dispersion is not considered a source of PN, its interplay with the system's PN results in aggravated signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) performance. This phenomenon is called equalization-enhanced phase noise (EEPN) [9] and it will also be a subject of study in this manuscript.

The compensation of PN is typically performed assuming that it is a Wiener random walk process [1], with a variance that depends on the system parameters. As a consequence of this random behavior, the compensation of PN implies estimating it over time with as much granularity as possible, ideally with a time step that should be significantly shorter than its autocorrelation width. With the general attention put into digital subcarrier-multiplexing (DSCM) systems, and the subsequent decrease of subcarrier-baud-rate, the design of CPR subsystems clearly needs to be put under consideration. In the paradigm shift from single-carrier to multi-subcarrier systems, the naive approach to DSP, in general, would be to treat the DSP chain for each subcarrier as if it were a single lower-baud-rate contributor. However, as one can easily infer, per-subcarrier approaches are suboptimal, since they do not fully use all the information they have access to. Sweeping through the literature, one can find a plethora of algorithms specifically designed for DSCM systems, either just making use of all the digital information available, or often even profiting from the particularities of these systems [10]–[12]. The CPR subsystem is no exception [13]–[18]. In [13], we find, for the first time, the study of a joint architecture to CPR. Having as a base the famous Viterbi & Viterbi CPR algorithm, it operates in a superchannel of Nyquist WDM carriers. Following on that, and now, for the first time, specifically for DSCM systems, [14] presents three different approaches for the joint DSCM CPR subsystem resorting to V&V: namely, the authors use as a baseline a subcarrier-independent CPR, and compare it against: i) a scenario in which the CPR is only performed for one subcarrier and the resulting PN estimate is used for correction in all remaining subcarriers; and ii) a scenario in which the result of the PN estimate among all subcarriers is averaged prior

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to compensation. In [15], a joint blind CPR algorithm is devised to be able to identify cycle slips in one of the DSCM subcarriers, a problem that may occur in blind CPR algorithms. In [16], the penalty of implementing subcarrier-independent CPR is assessed numerically, for pilot-aided CPR applied to higher-order modulation formats. A joint pilot-aided approach is devised, and it is shown that joint CPR can mitigate any penalty in terms of phase tracking associated with lower baud rates, when compared to the single-carrier system. In [17], joint CPR strategies are experimentally assessed, featuring joint pilot-aided CPR and joint blind CPR approaches, as first and second stages of the CPR. It was thus experimentally validated the applicability of joint CPR in practical systems. In [18], a CPR algorithm designed for DSCM systems, to tackle the issue of the interplay between phase noise and chromatic dispersion is presented.

In this manuscript, we aim to report a collection of state-of-the-art contributions to CPR and review all the relevant system aspects when designing a CPR DSP subsystem for long-haul coherent transmission. We intend to perform an unbiased analysis on the single-carrier vs. DSCM performance regarding the CPR, in both linear and nonlinear systems. To achieve such a goal, we have designed a consistent set of results with a simulation setup, and we compare several algorithms on the same data, yielding a fair comparison of the several approaches. The remainder of the manuscript takes the following structure: in Section II, we aim to provide the reader with a brief description of the workings of the most common CPR algorithms as initially designed, for single-carrier systems; in Section III, we further delve into the implementation of CPR algorithms, now with modifications such that the CPR algorithms are better tailored for DSCM systems; in Section IV, we focus on the performance of CPR algorithms on the linear channel, studying the robustness to an increase on laser linewidths and to EEPN; in Section V, we move to the performance of CPR algorithms on the nonlinear channel; finally, in Section VI, we draw the main conclusions from this work, and point out potential future directions for CPR-related research.

II. CARRIER-PHASE RECOVERY: BASIC CONCEPTS AND ALGORITHMS

Prior to the advent of digital algorithms for CPR as we know them today, an effort was made to use the well-established classical digital phase-locked loop (PLL) method for carrier recovery in optical communication systems. However, in the context of coherent optical systems, its complexity, low tolerance to regular laser linewidths, and susceptibility to nonlinear effects make it less preferred [19]–[21]. Coherent optical systems thus typically employ alternative approaches to achieve accurate and stable carrier recovery and demodulation. Such approaches must not only aim for lower complexity but also for faster phase tracking, to be able to compensate broader laser linewidths and NLPN.

In their essence, all CPR algorithms have a common goal: to achieve the best accuracy versus complexity trade-off in terms of compensating for the otherwise forbidding phase

noise. Two major classes can be identified when revising CPR algorithms, blind and pilot-aided. In this manuscript, we follow that division and further elaborate on why there can be interest in having a mix of both, resulting in a dual-stage CPR approach.

Notation: we utilize the following notation to describe common CPR algorithms and expressions: X_k and \hat{X}_k are the transmitted signal and the signal after carrier phase recovery; Y_k is the received signal prior to CPR; $(\cdot)^*$ represents the complex conjugate; $[\cdot]^D$ is the symbol decision; $E[\cdot]$ is the expected value; $\angle(\cdot)$ is the phase of a complex number; and $\text{Re}\{\cdot\}$ represents its real component.

A. Blind CPR

Blind CPR algorithms can perform phase noise estimation without knowledge of any specific symbol transmitted. However, they still require some knowledge about the modulation format of the signal. Some blind algorithms can be strongly modulation-format-dependent, i.e., their design only works for a given modulation format; others can be quasi-modulation-format-independent, requiring only minimal adaption to work with any modulation format.

Being blind, and, consequently, not requiring any overhead on the signal, comes at the expense of typically more complex algorithms, worse performance in low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) scenarios, and the occurrence of cycle-slips, in rotationally symmetric constellations. On the other hand, being able to track the phase noise at every symbol allows for the compensation of fast variations in the phase noise.

Among the most notable blind CPR algorithms, we highlight the following:

1) *Viterbi & Viterbi (V&V):* one of the first CPR algorithms applied in coherent optical communications [22], initially designed for m -phase shift keying (PSK) transmission, is the V&V algorithm. It is designed to benefit from the constant-modulus property of PSK systems. In Fig. 1, a diagram of the algorithm can be found for the case of QPSK transmission. The signal is raised to the fourth power and non-cumulative noise is filtered in a centered window of length L . Thanks to the particular geometry of the QPSK constellation, the signal after this operation has an angle equal to four times the phase noise we aim to compensate for without any dependence on the modulated data. Thus, compensation then is as trivial as the extraction of the phase of this signal, a division by four, and using this phase in the complex exponential multiplied by the received signal. Albeit being most known for its use in QPSK systems, note how it is easily extended to any m -PSK constellation, at the expense of a smaller unambiguous phase estimate region, replacing the fourth power by the m -th power, and respective division of the phase by m . Extensions of the V&V algorithm to higher-order square-QAM constellations have also been proposed [23], however, these have not gained much adhesion, due to weaker performance in these formats. Nevertheless, V&V is still a very attractive and typical choice for QPSK systems.

2) *Blind Phase Search (BPS):* BPS was proposed in [24]. It is known for being robust and versatile; however also known

Fig. 1. Diagram of the V&V algorithm.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the BPS algorithm, entailing (a) the block of a single test-phase, and (b) the overall algorithm, resulting of the selection of the best-performing test phase.

for its complexity. In Fig. 2, a diagram of the BPS algorithm is shown. It works by applying B test phase rotations, φ_b , to the received signal and measuring the error between the rotated signal before and after decoding, as can be seen in Fig. 2.a. Intuitively, the compensated signal at each time instant is the one that minimizes the mean square error caused by the decision, averaged over a window of L symbols. This choice among the several test phases is present in Fig. 2.b. This CPR is quasi-modulation-format-independent, in the sense that it can be applied to any modulation format by only changing the symbol decision block.

The main limitation of BPS is its complexity: for each test phase, we must perform a rotation of the signal, make a decision, and assess the resulting error. A simple way to keep its complexity low is to reduce the number of test phases, at the cost of a coarser phase estimation. Attempts to reduce the complexity of BPS without sacrificing performance are also found in the literature, with approaches such as using a simplified approximation to assess the error resultant of each test phase [25] or using a coarse BPS followed by a decision-directed maximum likelihood (ML) CPR [26], the latter which we describe next.

A relevant aspect regarding the performance of BPS in systems employing PCS is how its performance decreases with the increase in the shaping factor, and it has been reported that gains can be obtained from slightly detuning the optimal shaping factor [27], or even investigating alternatives to the classical Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution [8].

3) *Decision-Directed Maximum Likelihood (ML)*: if we know that the system is well-behaved in terms of phase noise, i.e., if the phase noise does not greatly surpass the neighborhood of a symbol, one far less complex approach

Fig. 3. Diagram of the ML algorithm.

Fig. 4. Diagram of the (a) transmitted symbol sequence, with unknown data and periodically inserted pilot symbols; (b) pilot-aided CPR. Note that the blocks with the dashed outlines operate only on pilot symbol indexes.

to CPR than the BPS is the ML [26], [28]–[30]. Note that this approach typically requires coarse estimations prior to it, since the decision is taken without any phase rotation, as in [26]. The workings of this CPR are showcased in Fig. 3. It estimates phase noise by performing a single symbol decision, and the filtered phase difference of the symbol before and after the decision is considered to be the phase noise. While this approach is clearly limited, and more prone to errors, it is far less complex than BPS, and may, therefore, be a sufficient solution in some applications, as we will study.

B. Pilot-Aided CPR

As seen above, available blind approaches to CPR compatible with high-order modulation formats often include at least one symbol decision for each symbol, which can drive the complexity up. On the other hand, if we allow for some overhead on the system, the complexity of CPR can be drastically reduced. Pilot-aided CPR [31], [32] works by interleaving pilot symbols in the signal after symbol mapping, occupying a symbol slot, and following a pilot-rate, R_P , of the form $1/(1+k)$, in which k represents the number of data symbols between two consecutive pilot symbols. A simplistic representation of this can be seen in Fig. 4.a. Typical pilot-rates are in the order of 3% [33]. The fact that the phase noise estimate is extracted from a symbol whose value is known in advance, makes this a straightforward and simple approach, and, inherently, modulation-format-independent. Pilot-aided CPR constitutes an attractive solution to CPR, when compared to blind CPR, thanks to its improved complexity vs. performance tradeoff.

In the standard pilot-based CPR, the pilot symbols follow the QPSK arrangement, inserted at the average signal power. The pilot-sequences are then predefined sequences of QPSK symbols that are known at the transmitter, and allow for ambiguity-free phase noise estimation, being only impaired by random noise. At the receiver DSP, CPR works as shown in Fig. 4.b, by simply extracting the phase difference between the known transmitted pilot sequences and the actual received signal. Since the signal has experienced random noise, though, filtering is performed on the phase noise estimate, with a

sliding window of length L . After filtering, the phase noise estimate is interpolated to have a phase noise value for each data symbol.

While not explored in this paper, and thus without a full subsection on the matter, it is still important to mention that pilot-aided CPR as described above is not the only approach to pilot-based CPR found in the literature. In [34], pilot-tone CPR is proposed. This CPR performs the phase recovery by extracting, at the receiver DSP, the phase of a pilot-tone inserted digitally at the baseband at the transmitter. Unlike in the pilot-aided CPR described above, in pilot-tone CPR, the tone is frequency division multiplexed, as opposed to time division multiplexed.

C. Dual-Stage CPR

We have now briefly revisited both blind and pilot-aided CPR strategies, and while both can work alone, often the best solution is not one or the other but rather a balanced combination of both [17], [35]. An initial pilot-aided CPR stage allows for a more noise-resilient and unambiguous phase noise tracking. Afterward, a blind stage allows for fine-grained and faster phase tracking. Multiple arrangements of different dual-stage CPR algorithms can be considered, typically formed by a pilot-based approach followed by a BPS [35], [36] or ML [37] second stage. Nevertheless, other fully-blind multi-stage CPR combinations have also been reported in the literature, such as BPS followed by ML [26], V&V followed by ML [38], [39], two-stage V&V [23], one/two-stage V&V followed by two-stage ML [40], [41], BPS followed by V&V with QPSK constellation transformation [42] and BPS preceded by a decision-directed feedback [43].

III. CARRIER-PHASE RECOVERY FOR MULTI-SUBCARRIER OPTICAL SYSTEMS

As aforementioned, the simpler approach to phase recovery in multi-subcarrier systems is to merely address the CPR subsystem in each subcarrier independently, as if it were a lower baud rate single-carrier system. Under this paradigm, any of the CPR algorithms previously addressed in Section II can be likewise applied to DSCM systems. Throughout the manuscript, this approach will be referred to as *per-SC CPR*. Logically, it is to be expected that plain per-SC CPR processing leads to suboptimal performance, since we are not using all the information available at the receiver. Instead, in multi-subcarrier systems phase recovery can also be addressed through joint processing among multiple subcarriers¹, whose paradigm is denominated in this paper as *joint-SC CPR* processing. A revision of the most relevant state-of-the-art joint-SC CPR approaches is provided, considering both pilot-aided and blind CPR strategies.

A. Pilot-Aided Joint-Subcarrier CPR Algorithms

Building upon the per-SC pilot-aided CPR of Fig. 4, a joint-SC pilot-aided CPR can be straightforwardly implemented by

¹Note that, for the sake of simplicity, all CPR implementations were done on a per-polarization basis. Nevertheless, it is important to mention that joint-polarization processing can also be applied to enhance CPR performance, which is similarly applicable both to single-carrier and subcarrier-multiplexed systems.

Fig. 5. Example of how the phase estimate from the per-SC CPR can be averaged to achieve a single, improved, phase noise estimate to all subcarriers.

Fig. 6. Pilot symbols positioning across the N_{SC} subcarriers in different strategies. In this diagram, each square represents a time-frequency block corresponding to a symbol.

performing the phase averaging process across all subcarriers composing the DSCM system, as depicted in Fig. 5. Note that this joint-SC CPR paradigm implies that the same phase noise compensation is commonly applied to all DSCM subcarriers. This implies that the estimated phase noise must be frequency-independent, which is a valid assumption for memoryless linear systems, as will be explored further ahead. While joint-SC pilot-aided CPR can be universally described by the schematic of Fig. 5, several practical implementation variants can be obtained by considering different arrangements of the pilot symbol positions within the DSCM signal, as discussed in the following.

1) *Synced Pilots Joint CPR (jPIL-sync)*: similar to one of the joint approaches presented in [14], the less demanding approach to joint CPR would be, without changing anything at the transmitter level (without changing pilot symbols placement), to average the several phase noise estimates from all the subcarrier's pilot-aided CPR to achieve a single more noise resilient estimate of the phase noise. This means that the pilot symbols distribution follows the placement named *PIL-synced* in Fig. 6. Regarding the positioning of the pilot symbols, we can see how this approach has the advantage of being with the standards for single-carrier, as it does not require subcarrier-specific indexing. However, this may be suboptimum in terms of time resolution for rapid phase tracking. In this manuscript, we call this approach *jPIL-sync*.

2) *Spaced Pilots Joint CPR (jPIL-spaced)*: as explored in [16], [17], [44] the relative arrangement of pilots among subcarriers can play a relevant role when performing joint CPR. In [17], spaced-pilots CPR, henceforward referred to as jPIL-spaced, is presented as an approach to pilot-aided joint-subcarrier CPR that consists of obtaining a (single) phase noise estimate from the pilot symbols inserted in all subcarriers. As displayed in Fig. 6, under the name of *PIL-spaced*, for better time granularity, we strategically place the pilot symbols with offset indexes among subcarriers, as opposed to placing them always at the same symbol index. We do this with the intuition that, doing so, we get more frequent unambiguous phase tracking. The operation of this CPR is very similar to the jPIL-sync approach, differing only on the indexes of the pilots. Note that, in spite of changing the pilot symbols indexing, they still follow the same pilot-rate R_P in each subcarrier.

3) *Single-Reference Subcarrier (SRS)*: also presented in [14], [17], yet another approach to joint CPR is the single reference subcarrier approach, SRS. The advantages of the SRS CPR are twofold: not only it presents the benefits of a joint CPR approach, but also the CPR subsystem can now extract a phase noise estimate from the operation on a single subcarrier. For this goal, all the pilot-symbols usually allocated among the several subcarriers are now placed in that single reference subcarrier, as demonstrated under the label *PIL-SRS*, in Fig. 6.

4) *Dual-Reference Subcarrier (DRS)*: another implementation of joint CPR is the DRS approach [18]. Unlike the previous CPR designs, which assume the phase noise to be a purely random walk with no structure, DRS CPR goes a step further, by making the CPR chromatic dispersion-aware. It does so by realizing that, due to fiber dispersion, different frequency components of the system will suffer from a different combination of the transmitter and receiver phase noises, because the subcarriers arrive to the receiver with a time-shift among them. We refer to this time-shift as a subcarrier *walk-off*, and, in a linear system, the phase noise experienced by subcarrier k after CD compensation is given by:

$$\phi_k(t) = \phi_{\text{TX}}(t) + \phi_{\text{LO}}(t - kT_{\text{CD}}), \quad (1)$$

where ϕ_{TX} and ϕ_{LO} are the contributions of the transmitter and LO lasers, respectively, and T_{CD} is the walk-off between two adjacent subcarriers. In [18], a CPR algorithm is devised stemming from this realization. Requiring only two reference subcarriers, to which all the pilot-symbols are equally allocated, and maintaining the same overall pilot-rate, the DRS CPR can separate the transmitter (Tx) and local oscillator (LO) contributions to phase noise. This allows to perform the correct phase noise compensation by properly combining the Tx and LO contributions according to the walk-off perceived by each subcarrier, as shown in Fig. 7. Note that, from all the joint CPR approaches known to the authors, this is the only approach where, albeit joint, the compensation is performed with different overall phase noise estimates for each subcarrier, resulting from a linear combination of the Tx and LO phase noise estimates. Moreover, Fig. 7 shows,

Fig. 7. Diagram of the DRS CPR. The reconstruction of ϕ_{TX} and ϕ_{LO} is done according to [18]. The blocks with $z^{-T_{\text{CD}}}$ implement the subcarrier walk-off delay. Blocks in dashed lines are an optional addition to the originally proposed DRS, with H_{CD} and CDC implementing the transfer function of the chromatic dispersion and respective compensation.

Fig. 8. Adaption of BPS algorithm to perform jointly across subcarriers. All the blocks implement the same function as in the previously described BPS.

in dashed lines, an optional addition to the baseline DRS algorithm, which aims to mitigate EEPN when the effect of intra-subcarrier CD is not negligible. To achieve such a goal, we digitally reapply chromatic dispersion to each subcarrier, then compensate for the LO phase noise. Afterward, we revert the digitally applied CD, and compensate for the Tx phase noise. While this addition clearly increases the complexity of the CPR, we study it in the manuscript to explore how much of the intra-subcarrier effect of EEPN can be mitigated.

B. Blind Joint-Subcarrier CPR Algorithms

In a similar fashion to pilot-aided CPR, blind CPR can also be adapted to be performed jointly (with the main difference being that there are no pilot symbols to be allocated).

1) *Joint BPS (jBPS)*: in [17], two implementations to perform BPS jointly are proposed, but similar performance was reported; thus, in this manuscript, we will only study one for simplicity. We will then consider the BPS version that operates by selecting the test phase that minimizes not only the average error among a centered window of L symbols, but also across N_{SC} subcarriers [17]. A scheme of how this is performed is shown in Fig. 8.

2) *Joint ML (jML)*: while we have not identified any report of the implementation of the ML algorithm jointly, it is deemed a trivial adaptation from the regular ML algorithm described in Section II.A, with the small modification that the phase noise estimate is averaged not only on a window of L

Fig. 9. Adaption of the ML algorithm to perform jointly across subcarriers.

Fig. 10. CPR subsystem under different approaches to dual-stage CPR in DSCM systems. We study the case when: (a) both CPR stages are performed independently per subcarrier; (b) the first, pilot-aided, stage is performed jointly but the second is performed per subcarrier; and (c) both CPR stages are performed jointly.

symbols, but also across the N_{SC} subcarriers, as is shown in Fig. 9.

C. Dual-Stage Joint-Subcarrier CPR Algorithms

After the first-stage of pilot-aided CPR, per subcarrier or joint, we can have a joint second-stage CPR, further benefitting from the advantages of joint DSP. The different combinations studied in this manuscript can be found in Fig. 10 (a), (b), and (c). The typical approach against which we may be interested in performing a comparison is represented by path (a), where both first-stage, pilot-aided, and second-stage, blind, CPRs use a subcarrier-independent method. From there, we study the cases in which, following a joint first-stage CPR, we perform either a per-SC or a joint second-stage CPR, represented in paths (b) and (c), respectively. While solution (c) is expected to improve the SNR tolerance of the blind algorithms, as verified in [14], it is important to keep in mind that it might not be optimal for NLPN compensation, due to its frequency dependence [3], which might eventually benefit from the solution represented by (b), as will be exploited further ahead in Section V.

IV. CARRIER-PHASE RECOVERY IN LINEAR FIBER CHANNELS

A. Description of Simulation Setup

The numerical results presented in this work have been obtained by employing the simulation setup depicted in Fig. 11. The transmitter generates a WDM signal composed of 5 independent dual-polarization channels, each of which is modulated with a given modulation format (QPSK, 16QAM

or PCS-64QAM) at a symbol-rate of 256 Gbaud. When using 16QAM, this yields a gross bit-rate of 2.048 Tbps per channel, which would correspond to a net bit-rate of 1.6 Tbps when the typical employing 20% FEC overhead in addition to an overall 1/16 overhead for other pilot symbols and/or training sequences. The same bit-rate is considered for the PCS-64QAM modulation option, leading to a constellation entropy of 4.33(3) bits per symbol. Instead, the QPSK modulated signal (to be considered only further ahead as a reference for NLPN impact) takes a halved gross bit-rate of 1.024 Tbps, which would correspond to a net bit-rate of 800 Gbps under the same considerations made above. For every WDM channel, a total of 2^{19} symbols are simulated, divided by the number of subcarriers, and, accordingly, we divide the overall symbol-rate into N_{sc} subcarriers, composing a DSCM signal. Then, for each subcarrier, symbol mapping is performed according to the defined QAM format, followed by root-raised cosine (RRC) pulse shaping with 0.05 roll-off. All subcarriers are multiplexed into the corresponding WDM channel, and laser phase noise is added (only for the LPN and EEPN studies) employing a Wiener process with a variance given by

$$\sigma_{f_{\text{TX}}}^2 = 2\pi\Delta f_{\text{TX}}/R_s, \quad (2)$$

where Δf_{TX} is the laser linewidth and R_s the subcarrier baud rate. Finally, all 5 WDM channels are multiplexed on a channel grid of 275 GHz.

The optical link is then composed of N_{spans} spans of standard single-mode fiber (SSMF) whose parameters (attenuation – α ; group velocity dispersion – β_2 ; nonlinear coefficient – γ ; and span length – L_{span}) are indicated in Table I, depending on the application scenario under test. Namely, when studying the impact and mitigation of LPN alone, each fiber span is simplified into a simple attenuation. Conversely, when studying the impact of EEPN, the effect of chromatic dispersion is added. Finally, for the analysis of the impact and mitigation of NLPN (see section V), the Kerr nonlinearity is also included, in which case a split-step Fourier method simulation is performed to implement the Manakov equation. In all cases, after each fiber span, an inline EDFA is inserted with a given gain, G_{EDFA} , and noise figure, NF_{EDFA} , as defined in Table I.

After transmission over the optical link, the central wavelength, i.e. the channel under test (CUT), is extracted from the WDM signal and mixed with a local oscillator (LO), which adds a second laser phase noise component. For simplicity, in this work, we will always consider that the Tx and LO lasers have the same linewidth. The received signal is then fed to the DSP chain, which includes chromatic dispersion compensation (CDC)², DSCM demultiplexing, matched filtering and carrier-phase recovery. For all the studied scenarios, the length of the CPR filtering window, L , has been optimized. Finally, the performance is assessed in terms of average normalized generalized mutual information (NGMI) among all subcarriers [45], which is then converted into an

²In this work, we have used full-spectrum CDC, i.e., the time delay among digital subcarriers imposed by CD was also compensated for. Nevertheless, thanks to the symmetry Tx laser—CD—Rx laser, most conclusions drawn regarding CPR still hold true regardless of using full or intra-subcarrier CDC.

Fig. 11. Simulation setup utilized in this work, including transmitter DSP, optical link and receiver DSP subsystems.

TABLE I
OPTICAL LINK PARAMETERS UTILIZED FOR THE LPN, EEPN AND NLPN
NUMERICAL ANALYSES

	LPN	EEPn	NLPN
α (dB/km)		0.2	
β_2 (ps ² /km)	0	-20.4	
γ (1/(W.km))		0	1.3
L_{span} (km)		100	
G_{EDFA} (dB)		20	
NF _{EDFA} (dB)		5	

equivalent signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). This value of SNR thus accounts not only for amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise but also for DSP and PN penalties.

B. Impact and Mitigation of Laser Phase Noise

Let us start our numerical analysis by addressing the standalone impact of laser phase noise, which has been the primary driving factor for CPR developments during the last decade. For simplicity, we will consider the use of a fixed pilot-rate of 1/32 (3.125% overhead), which is a standard option in most coherent DSP applications and standards [33].

The SNR performance of different single- and dual-stage CPR algorithms over a linear dispersionless optical link is shown in Fig. 12. Here, we consider a launched power per channel of 6 dBm and an optical link composed of 24 fiber + EDFA sections. The corresponding AWGN theoretical SNR limit is also shown in Fig. 12 as an upper performance bound, and it corresponds to an optical SNR (OSNR) of 25.2 dB. Note that all the reported SNRs for the best-performing CPRs are above the required SNR for post-FEC error-free communication, accounting for the 20% FEC overhead (with an NGMI threshold of 0.88). The impact of the number of subcarriers on the SNR performance after CPR is first illustrated in Fig. 12a, considering a combined laser linewidth of 200 kHz. Three broad categories of CPR algorithms are compared therein: i) per-subcarrier pilot-based CPR (PIL); ii) per-subcarrier pilot-based CPR followed by a 2nd blind stage (PIL + BPS and PIL + ML); and iii) joint-subcarrier pilot-based CPR (jPIL-synced, jPIL-spaced and jPIL-SRS). The first key observation from Fig. 12a is that the joint-SC strategies clearly outperform the per-SC CPR as the number of subcarriers increases. Note that the

standalone pilot-based CPR (PIL) with the designated pilot-rate of 1/32 already starts to yield a performance penalty of more than 0.1 dB with only 4 subcarriers (64 Gbaud each), and this penalty quickly ramps up with an increasing number of subcarriers. It can therefore be concluded that single-stage per-SC pilot-based CPR is not adequate for DSCM signals even with a low to moderate number of subcarriers.

By adding a 2nd blind CPR stage using either the ML or BPS algorithms, we observe that the performance penalty associated with per-SC processing can be pushed forward to a larger number of subcarriers, enabling roughly penalty-free operation (when compared with joint-SC processing) for up to 8 subcarriers, i.e. 32 Gbaud per SC. However, as the baud rate per subcarrier is further reduced, the dual-stage per-SC CPR shows a similar performance penalty trend as its single-stage counterpart.

Clearly, for $N_{\text{sc}} \geq 16$ joint-SC CPR provides the adequate processing paradigm, enabling to roughly maintain single-carrier-like performance regardless of the number of DSCM subcarriers. Among the considered joint-SC CPR variants, we can observe that the jPIL-synced algorithm, which uses the default pilot symbol distribution inherited from single-carrier systems, starts to become suboptimal for a large number of subcarriers (above 32), owing to the loss of timing resolution on the CPR estimates. In that regard, the use of a subcarrier-spaced (jPIL-spaced) or single reference subcarrier (jPIL-SRS) pilot distribution, as previously described in Fig. 6, allows to circumvent this issue by reducing the time gaps between pilot symbols.

Considering now the most challenging condition in Fig. 12a, corresponding to the use of 64 subcarriers, the impact of the combined laser linewidth is shown in Fig 12b, where the same CPR strategies are again compared. Here, similar conclusions can be drawn, namely regarding the quickly increasing performance penalty of the standalone pilot-based CPR. Again, its dual-stage variants can only delay the performance loss effect, but follow the same trend. In turn, the joint-SC strategies always provide the best performance, with the jPIL-synced becoming suboptimal for combined laser linewidths above 100 kHz, for the same reasoning explained above. Additionally, with a broader laser linewidth horizon, we can also identify that jPIL-spaced underperforms comparatively to the jPIL-SRS. We hypothesize this

Fig. 12. Impact and mitigation of laser phase noise using a dual-stage CPR (pilot-based followed by a 2nd blind stage). The transmitted signal is modulated as uniform 16QAM at 256 GBaud. The pilot overhead is fixed at 3.125% (1/32 pilot-rate), the transmitted power is 6 dBm and the link length is 2400 km. The transmission is performed over an ideal AWGN channel, i.e. no chromatic dispersion or nonlinearities are considered, thus isolating the impact of LPN. Transmitter and LO lasers are considered to have the same laser linewidth. a) and b) show obtained SNR after processing as a function of number of subcarriers at a fixed combined laser linewidth of 200 kHz (a) and as a function of combined laser linewidth for 64 subcarriers (b); c) and d) show the gain provided by the 2nd CPR stage as a function of the number of subcarriers (c) and combined laser linewidth (d).

difference may surface from the phase noise estimate interpolation block, to which only the $jPIL$ -spaced is subject.

Finally, the gain provided by a 2nd stage blind CPR when applied over the joint-SC pilot-based algorithm is analyzed in Figs. 12c and 12d, considering again the impact of the number of subcarriers and combined laser linewidth, respectively. Two main CPR strategies are considered here, following on what was discussed regarding Fig. 10, where a joint-SC CPR ($jPIL$ -SRS) is followed by a 2nd stage consisting of either i) a per-SC blind CPR (BPS or ML) or ii) a joint-SC blind CPR ($jBPS$ or jML). As one might expect, it becomes clear from the analysis of Figs. 12c and 12d that the application of a per-SC 2nd stage over a joint-SC 1st stage is ineffective, leading to virtually no impact on the system. Instead, the use of joint-SC 2nd stage is shown to enable further performance improvement, becoming significantly more relevant for a high number of subcarriers and large laser linewidth. Namely, with 64 subcarriers and 2 MHz combined laser linewidth (e.g. corresponding to the use of DFB lasers in the Tx and LO), the 2nd stage joint-SC CPR can provide more than 0.3 dB gain. In this regard, and also revisiting all numerical results in Fig. 12, it is interesting to note that the ML and BPS algorithms tend to yield similar performances in the considered scenarios. Here, it is important to note that the BPS algorithm has been set with 16 test phases within an angular range of $\pi/16$, which was found to saturate its performance. Therefore, despite some marginal gain of BPS (roughly less than 0.1 dB in all assessed cases), the ML CPR might be an attractive alternative in terms of tradeoff between performance and computational complexity, since it avoids the test phases sweep that is required by BPS.

C. Equalization-Enhanced Phase Noise: Origin and Impact

In high-baud-rate long-haul dispersion unmanaged systems, symbols can easily suffer a spreading in the orders of the thousands of symbols. And the LO phase noise will be imprinted in this dispersed signal. As a consequence, when

performing CDC, we are desirably removing the effects of CD on the transmitted signal, but simultaneous- and undesirably imposing the inverse CD's transfer function in the phase noise component of the LO. The LO phase noise becomes enhanced by CD equalization, hence EEPN. This phase noise distortion results in a penalty in the ability to compensate for PN if the effect of CD is not negligible.

In [46], an expression is derived for the effective phase noise variance of a linear optical system suffering from EEPN, consisting of three separable terms:

$$\sigma_f^2 = \underbrace{2\pi\Delta f_{TX}/R_s}_{\sigma_{f_{TX}}^2} + \underbrace{2\pi\Delta f_{LO}/R_s}_{\sigma_{f_{LO}}^2} + \underbrace{\beta_2\pi^2 L\Delta f_{LO}R_s}_{\sigma_{f_{EEP}}^2}, \quad (3)$$

where Δf_{TX} and Δf_{LO} represent the transmitter's and LO's laser linewidths, respectively, L is the transmission length, and R_s is the subcarrier baud rate. Historically, PN has only been modeled accounting for the two first terms, $\sigma_{f_{TX}}^2$ and $\sigma_{f_{LO}}^2$. These terms are inversely proportional to the subcarrier's baud rate, and thus higher baud rate systems could seem like the better option. However, conversely, the contribution of the EEPN to the PN variance, $\sigma_{f_{EEP}}^2$, scales linearly with the baud rate, which benefits DSCM transmission.

Even though it is true that, indeed, DSCM will be less affected by EEPN, it will still experience an effect that is not captured by (3), but that is equally caused by how the LO phase noise is imprinted onto a dispersed signal, as we have seen in (1), and thus assuming that all subcarriers have suffered from the LO phase noise synchronously can lead to non-negligible penalty when this effect is not taken into account in joint CPR.

The impact of EEPN on system performance is depicted in Fig. 13a, considering a uniform 16QAM signal at 256 GBaud, transmitted over a dispersion unmanaged optical link. To simplify the illustration of the EEPN effect, we consider only the case of 8 subcarriers (i.e. 8×32 GBaud), together with two theoretical phase recovery approaches: i) a zero-forcing (ZF) phase recovery, in which the combined laser phase noise of the Tx and LO lasers is removed exactly as it was inserted

Fig. 13. Impact and mitigation of EEPN using a dual-stage CPR (pilot-based followed by a 2nd blind stage). The transmitted signal is modulated as uniform 16QAM at 256 GBaud. The pilot overhead is fixed at 3.125% (1/32 pilot-rate), the transmitted power is 6 dBm and the link length is 2400 km. Only linear fiber transmission is considered, i.e. chromatic dispersion is simulated and nonlinearities are ignored, thus isolating the impact of EEPN. Transmitter and LO lasers are considered to have the same laser linewidth. a) shows the dependence of SNR on the link length when employing 8 subcarriers and using a genie-aided zero forcing CPR. b) and c) show the obtained SNR after processing as a function of the number of subcarriers at a fixed combined laser linewidth of 200 kHz (b) and as a function of combined laser linewidth for 64 subcarriers (c).

into the signal, neglecting the effect of dispersion, and ii) the same ZF approach but combining the Tx and LO lasers on each subcarrier according to the corresponding walk-off effect that is created by CD, following (1). Complementary, the impact of EEPN on the received signal constellations is graphically depicted in Fig. 14 for the case of 8 subcarriers propagated over 10 spans of 100 km, using either approach i) or ii) mentioned above.

From Fig. 13a, we clearly observe that the standard ZF approach, which would correspond to an ideal CPR in the absence of chromatic dispersion, now leads to a significant penalty (roughly 1 dB) compared to the AWGN limit. This can be visually confirmed by the enhanced phase distortion that can be observed in the overall DSCM constellation shown in Fig. 14a, which results from the erroneous phase noise compensation that is applied to the edge DSCM subcarriers. Instead, properly combining the Tx and LO laser phase noises, taking into account the walk-off effect, enables us to reduce this penalty to about 0.2 dB. In fact, this residual penalty is caused by the impact of intra-subcarrier dispersion, which still creates some frequency-dependent dephasing effect between the Tx and LO phase noise contributions. To further reduce this penalty and achieve AWGN-like performance, the subcarrier bandwidth must be reduced, i.e. more subcarriers should be employed. This can be observed in Fig. 13b, where the ZF approach with walk-off factorization asymptotically converges to the AWGN limit with increasing number of subcarriers.

D. Mitigating EEPN with DSCM and Joint-SC CPR

Still in Fig. 13b, corresponding to a fixed link length of 2400 km, we compare different pilot-based CPR strategies, to assess their performance in EEPN-impaired scenarios. The first relevant observation is that the jPIL-SRS algorithm is largely suboptimal regardless of the number of subcarriers, achieving roughly the same performance as a standard ZF phase removal. Although not shown for simplicity, other joint-SC CPR approaches, such as jPIL-spaced and jPIL-synced tend to yield similar results. This is because the underlying premise behind the design of these joint-SC CPR strategies is that

Fig. 14. Graphical depiction of the impact of EEPN on the retrieved 16QAM constellations after propagation of a 256 GBaud DSCM signal composed of 8 subcarriers over 10×100 km dispersion-unmanaged link. a) constellation obtained with zero-forcing carrier-phase recovery, which would be ideal without CD; b) constellation obtained after zero-forcing carrier-phase recovery, but employing walk-off factorization between subcarriers.

the combined laser phase noise of Tx and LO lasers impacts all subcarriers in the same manner, while we have seen that is not the case. This also justifies why the standard per-SC PIL CPR is able to deliver a much better performance than joint-SC CPR. Notably, for a low number of subcarriers (1–4 in Fig. 13b), we observe that the PIL CPR is actually able to overcome the performance of the walk-off ZF approach, which can be attributed to the fact that the pilot-based CPR is actually able to partially compensate for the extra phase noise component that is created by EEPN on an intra-subcarrier basis, i.e. $\sigma_{f_{EEP\text{N}}}^2$ in expression (3). However, due to the progressive loss of temporal resolution, the per-SC PIL algorithm quickly starts to become penalized by the use of an increasing number of subcarriers, similar to the previous LPN-only analysis of Fig. 12. Therefore, an EEPN-resilient joint-SC CPR strategy must be employed when the baud rate per subcarrier is sufficiently low (roughly below 16–32 GBaud in the considered scenario), which sets the scene for the DRS CPR approach. Indeed, the jPIL-DRS algorithm is shown to achieve the best performance in the considered scenario, regardless of the number of subcarriers. It can also

be seen that, while some performance gain can be achieved by increasing the number of subcarriers from 2 to 8 (essentially by avoiding the impact of intra-subcarrier EEPN), the DRS performance then tends to stabilize for a higher number of subcarriers, revealing that the joint-SC operation is actually able to simultaneously deal with the progressive loss of time resolution and also with the walk-off between subcarriers. In order to further reduce the impact of EEPN at a low number of subcarriers, a modification to the DRS approach is proposed, where an intermediate CD compensation stage is included into the algorithm, so that the intra-subcarrier EEPN effect can be mitigated. Employing such a strategy, named in Fig. 13b as jPIL-DRS (w/ CD) , we observe that the EEPN penalty can be largely suppressed at 2 and 4 subcarriers, thus contributing to extend the range of operation for the DSCM signal.

Finally, in Fig. 13c, we assess the impact of increasing the combined laser linewidth (same Tx and LO linewidths for simplicity) for the fixed scenario of 64 subcarriers. Similar conclusions can be taken, namely regarding the superior performance of the DRS CPR, regardless of the considered combined laser linewidth. On top of that, we have also introduced a second-stage joint-SC ML approach, jPIL-DRS + jML , which is able to provide roughly 0.1–0.2 dB of extra SNR performance, depending on the combined laser linewidth.

V. CARRIER-PHASE RECOVERY IN NONLINEAR FIBER CHANNELS

A. Nonlinear Phase Noise: Origin and Impact

As we know from the nonlinear Schrödinger equation modeling the propagation of a complex signal in the optical fiber [47], fiber nonlinearities arise from the non-constant instantaneous power of the transmitted signal. The interplay of fiber nonlinearities with chromatic dispersion makes this an intricate phenomenon and tough to compensate for. When the signal is sufficiently dispersed, the Gaussian noise (GN) model [48] predicts that a signal's modulation format no longer plays a relevant role in the nonlinear performance. But, since part of the propagation is done with the signal without significant dispersion, a correction term to the GN model is required. This correction term gives us an insight into how NLPN impact changes given the statistics of a modulation format [48], namely, the NLPN impact is expected to increase with the *kurtosis* of the signal, defined as:

$$\mu_4 = \frac{\mathbb{E}[|X_k|^4]}{\mathbb{E}[|X_k|^2]^2} \quad (4)$$

Note that, besides the signal's kurtosis, there is another relevant factor when aiming to speculate the impact of NLPN in a signal, which is the signal baud rate. The baud rate plays a relevant role because it dictates how quickly into the propagation the signal will be sufficiently dispersed, how quickly it approaches the GN assumption, which is the foundation for the effectiveness of symbol-rate optimization [49].

The dependence of SNR on the launched power per subcarrier is depicted in Fig. 15a, where different DSCM

Fig. 15. Impact of modulation format and number of subcarriers on the received signal SNR after transmission over 30×100 km of SSMF, without any CPR, i.e. applying only a constant phase rotation. a) SNR measured over the amplitude and phase (standard SNR) and only over the amplitude (neglects phase noise). b) penalty associated with NLPN, corresponding to the SNR difference between “amplitude-only” and “amplitude and phase” SNRs in a).

signal configurations are compared, including 1, 4, 16 and 64 subcarriers employing QPSK, 16QAM and PCS-64QAM modulations. Fiber propagation is performed over 3000 km (30×100 km) and the receiver-side processing is limited to matched filtering and a simple constant phase rotation (i.e. no actual CPR is employed in this stage). In order to isolate the impact of NLPN, two different SNR definitions are considered: i) the standard SNR that is measured over the amplitude and phase of the complex-valued optical signal, and ii) a phase noise-independent SNR, in which the phase component is assumed to be equal to that of the amplitude, as

$$\text{SNR}_{\text{amp}} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[|X_k|^2]}{2 \mathbb{E} \left[\text{Re} \left\{ (X_k - \hat{X}_k) \exp(-j\angle X_k) \right\}^2 \right]}. \quad (5)$$

By using the SNR_{amp} definition, we aim to provide an upper bound of performance that could be achievable without the

Fig. 16. Graphical depiction of the retrieved signal constellations after propagation over 10×100 km of SSMF at 8 dBm per channel. Only a constant phase rotation is applied at the receiver.

impact of *excess phase noise*³. The intuition behind this metric is that, assuming ideal phase compensation, the constellation noise should have a Gaussian distribution. Hence, the phase and amplitude components of the noise shall be equal in power. Thus, the upper bound for SNR with ideal phase correction can be obtained by considering that the total noise power is twice the amplitude/phase noise power.

Complementary to Fig. 15a, the SNR penalty induced by NLPN, i.e. the difference between the amplitude-only and amplitude-and-phase SNR, is shown in Fig. 15b. As a whole, the following main conclusions can be drawn from the analysis of Fig. 15:

- i) the impact of NLPN on the QPSK modulated signal is almost negligible when operating in single-carrier mode at 256 Gbaud, owing to the constant modulus property of this format, which minimizes the kurtosis in expression (4). Although the impact of NLPN on QPSK tends to increase with the number of subcarriers, a modest maximum penalty of ~ 0.2 dB is found at the optimum power with 64 subcarriers, revealing that QPSK is rather insensitive to the NLPN effect in long-haul dispersion unmanaged optical links, as can be visually confirmed by comparing the QPSK constellations with 1 and 64 SCs in Figs. 16a and 16d. For this reason, the SRO effect finds its peak gain with QPSK modulation, enabling an SNR increase with 64 subcarriers of roughly 0.8 dB w.r.t. single-carrier;
- ii) with 16QAM modulation, the impact of NLPN is significantly increased when compared with the constant modulus reference (QPSK), owing to its larger kurtosis, which results in non-negligible amplitude modulation to phase modulation conversion during nonlinear fiber transmission, as clearly observed in Figs. 16b and 16e.

³Note that the factor of 2 in the denominator of expression (5) actually implies the duplication of the amplitude noise into the phase noise component, thus corresponding to a perfectly Gaussian noise distribution whose variance is solely dictated by the amplitude noise component.

While the NLPN impact in single-carrier is limited below 0.2 dB, after 64 subcarriers, this penalty increases towards roughly 0.5 dB. As a result, the SRO effect becomes attenuated to approximately 0.5 dB net gain.

- iii) finally, owing to the quasi-Gaussian modulation promoted by PCS-64QAM, the kurtosis is strongly boosted, thus enhancing the NLPN effect and resulting in a significant performance penalty: from 0.3 dB penalty with single-carrier up to 0.9 dB with 64 subcarriers at the optimum power. The detrimental impact of NLPN with large number of subcarriers can be visually confirmed in Fig. 16f, corresponding to 64 subcarriers, mainly when compared against its single-carrier version depicted in Fig. 16c. As a result, the SRO effect is almost completely lost, leading to only ~ 0.1 dB residual gain.

As an overall picture, it becomes clear from the analysis of Fig. 15 that the NLPN effect constitutes a major limitation in DSCM signals with high subcarrier count, mainly when employing quasi-Gaussian modulation, as is the case of PCS-64QAM. It is, therefore, relevant to assess the actual capability of practical CPR algorithms to partially mitigate the impact of the otherwise hindering NLPN, as will be thoroughly addressed in the following section.

B. Mitigating Nonlinear Phase Noise Using CPR

Let us now assess the effectiveness of different CPR strategies on the mitigation of NLPN. To this end, we focus on the launch power of 8 dBm per channel, resulting in an operating OSNR of 26.2 dB. In Figs. 17a and 17b, we show the obtained SNR after processing with different CPR algorithms for the uniform 16QAM and PCS-64QAM formats, respectively. Similarly to the previous NLPN impact analysis of Fig. 15, here we keep the constant phase rotation curves obtained with amplitude-only and amplitude-and-phase SNR. These two reference curves can be used as upper and lower bounds of performance, respectively, i.e. the first corresponds to an ideal CPR that would completely remove the excess phase noise generated by NLPN, while the second corresponds to an NLPN-agnostic CPR that only tracks the long-term average phase rotation. Within these bounds, different pilot-based CPR strategies are compared, namely i) per-SC CPR (PIL); ii) joint-SC CPR using either spaced pilots ($j_{\text{PIL-spaced}}$), a single reference subcarrier ($j_{\text{PIL-SRS}}$) or a dual-reference subcarrier ($j_{\text{PIL-DRS}}$). For both the 16QAM and PCS-64QAM results, it can be concluded that the joint-SC pilot-based CPR provides some performance gain over standard per-SC processing, reaching up to 0.2 dB with 64 subcarriers. This shows that, despite the imperfect correlation between the NLPN contributions of different subcarriers (see e.g. reference [3]), the residual similitude of phase noise processes is still sufficiently strong to justify the use of joint-SC processing. It is also important to re-emphasize that the NLPN effect has been isolated in this numerical study (i.e. no laser phase noise has been simulated here), thus constituting a worst-case scenario for joint-SC processing. In a realistic scenario where both LPN and NLPN are considered together, it is expected that the scene for joint-SC processing will be somewhere in between the results obtained in Figs. 13 and 15.

Fig. 17. Impact and mitigation of NLPN using a dual-stage CPR (pilot-based followed by a 2nd blind stage), considering both uniform 16QAM and PCS-64QAM transmission. The pilot overhead is fixed at 3.125% (1/32 pilot-rate), the transmitted power is 8 dBm and the link length is 3000 km. Both chromatic dispersion and Kerr nonlinearities are simulated, while laser phase noise is neglected, thus isolating the impact of NLPN. a) and b) show the obtained SNR after processing as a function of the number of subcarriers for uniform 16QAM (a) and PCS-64QAM (b); c) and d) show the corresponding residual NLPN-induced penalty after CPR, also for uniform 16QAM (c) and PCS-64QAM (d).

Another interesting observation from Figs. 17a and 17b is that the DRS CPR still provides the best performance among all considered pilot-based CPR approaches, which further extends its region of validity into the nonlinear propagation regime (at least considering transmission at the optimum launched power, 8 dBm per channel in this case). Here, it is also important to recall that the standard EEPN effect, caused by the interplay between laser phase noise and chromatic dispersion, is absent in this study (since no LPN is considered). Nevertheless, the distributed generation of NLPN along the link can still somehow interact with chromatic dispersion, leading to some form of *nonlinear EEPN* effect. While the standard DRS operating principle of separating Tx and LO phase contributions is not directly applicable in this scenario, the same process can still partially compensate for the NLPN-CD interactions that have occurred in the first and second halves of the link. From the authors' perspective, this is the most likely reason for the observed performance gain with the DRS algorithm in Figs. 17a and 17b. It also opens the door for some potential modifications to the DRS algorithm, aiming at the design of an NLPN-tailored CPR. Although outside the scope of this paper, this constitutes a promising future research direction into the optimization of CPR for nonlinear fiber transmission.

Complementary to the above SNR-based analysis, in Figs. 17c and 17d, we show the residual NLPN-induced penalty that is left behind after CPR, which corresponds to the gap between the CPR curves in Figs. 17a and 17b and the corresponding amplitude-only SNR upper bound. For simplicity, we keep only the best-performing $jPIL-DRS$ curve, and we add a 2nd stage ML-based CPR, either performed on a per-SC ($jPIL-DRS + ML$) or joint-SC basis ($jPIL-DRS + jML$). Here, the most revealing conclusion is that a per-SC 2nd stage is preferable over a joint-SC approach. Although apparently contradictory with the improved joint-SC performance previously obtained with the pilot-based CPR stage, this result can be justified by the following reasoning:

- i) while pilot-based joint-SC processing benefits from a significant improvement in terms of time resolution

for CPR estimates (from 1 phase estimation every 32 symbols with the standard per-SC PIL approach up to 1 phase estimation every symbol with $jPIL-DRS$ at 64 subcarriers), the same gain does not apply to the 2nd stage CPR, which already inherently operates on a per-symbol basis. Then the lack of perfect correlation between the NLPN processes of different subcarriers might overshadow the benefit of joint-SC processing in this case;

- ii) by using a 1st stage joint-SC pilot-based CPR, which then applies the *same*⁴ phase noise compensation across all subcarriers, the common-mode NLPN effects are mostly compensated, leaving behind the SC-specific NLPN distortion. In other words, the cross-correlation between the NLPN processes of different subcarriers is expected to reduce after the 1st stage joint-SC CPR, which weakens the applicability of a 2nd stage joint-CPR approach.

Finally, to conclude the NLPN compensation study, in Fig. 18 we assess the impact of the pilot-rate on the residual NLPN penalty after CPR for the worst-case scenario of 64 subcarriers. Per-SC (PIL) and joint-SC ($jPIL-DRS$) approaches are compared for pilot overheads in the range of 1.5625% (1/64 pilot-rate) up to 50% (1/2 pilot-rate). Notably, for the $jPIL-DRS$ case, the pilot assignment to two subcarriers actually becomes saturated for pilot-rates above 1/32, in which case the two reference subcarriers are fully filled with pilot symbols, while the remaining 62 subcarriers are pilot-free. Even so, we find that the $jPIL-DRS$ still provides better performance than the per-SC PIL CPR for pilot overheads up to 25% and 50%, for the PCS-64QAM and uniform 16QAM use cases, respectively. Also, we find that the gain provided by the 2nd stage per-SC ML CPR tends to vanish as the pilot overhead increases. For instance, with PCS-64QAM, the lowest NLPN penalty of roughly 0.65 dB is achieved with a 50% overhead pilot-based CPR, whereas the

⁴Actually, by accounting for the walk-off effect, the DRS-CPE applies a different phase noise compensation to each subcarrier. Nevertheless, the estimated Tx and LO phase noises are still common to all subcarriers.

Fig. 18. Impact of pilot overhead on the residual NLPN penalty after CPR, considering the use of 64 subcarriers under the same conditions employed in Fig. 15 (3000 km, 8 dBm per channel).

2nd stage ML becomes ineffective. The limited performance exposed from these results, even considering unrealistically large pilot overheads, clearly unveils that there is still a long way to go before multi-carrier CPR can properly deal with NLPN-induced penalties, thus motivating the urgent need for further advances in CPR algorithms.

VI. CONCLUSION

Since the early stages of digital coherent optical receivers, carrier-phase recovery has been playing a central role within the DSP subsystem, motivating the design and validation of a plethora of novel algorithms tailored to the specificities of optical fiber communications. While the original challenge for carrier-phase recovery has been centered around the mitigation of laser phase noise, after more than a decade of rapid progress, new challenges are now on the table. Nowadays, the design of CPR algorithms should not only take into account the impact of laser phase noise, but also its interaction with the linear and nonlinear distortions generated during fiber propagation. Namely, the detrimental impacts of the EEPN and NLPN effects have motivated a paradigm change in the design of the optical signal itself, motivating the use of digital subcarrier multiplexing signals. While the advantages of DSCM are clear both in terms of linear and nonlinear transmission performance, their adoption implies a re-design of CPR algorithms to fully maximize the performance.

In this work, we have reviewed the most recent advances in digital CPR algorithms, mainly targeting their optimization for long-haul coherent optical systems, whose performance is ultimately limited by the EEPN and NLPN effects. In Section IV, when analyzing CPR in the linear regime, some encouraging results are found using CD-aware CPR, jPIL-DRS, which, together with DSCM signaling, is shown to effectively avoid the detrimental impact of EEPN. In turn, in Section IV, within the study of the nonlinear regime (i.e. at the optimum launched power) the effective mitigation of NLPN remains an open challenge. Although the exploitation of CD-aware CPR seems to unveil some promising direction,

significant work remains ahead, mainly when considering transmitted signals with dynamic range, as it is the case of probabilistic shaping constellations. It shall be noted that, while we chose to conduct the investigation of the linear and nonlinear effects on CPR separately, the jPIL-DRS algorithm was found to be the best performing option both in the linear and nonlinear regimes. Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that it should also provide the best performance in a realistic transmission system with the combined effects of LLW, CD and NLI.

In addition, future research on this topic will be highly constrained by the industry requirements in terms of power consumption. In this sense, any upgrades to the currently deployed CPR technology must imply minimal impact on energy consumption, thus precluding the use of complex nonlinear compensation strategies. Any achieved gain must always be weighted by the associated complexity. As typically shown by the recent history of optical fiber communications, the most effective solution to these challenges is likely to be achieved by finding the perfect balance between DSP engineering and physical knowledge of the system.

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